

Research

Narrative Analysis of Teachers' Experiences in the Implementation of Free Primary Education Policy in Myanmar

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Abstract: This article aims to analyze the teachers' experiences in the Pyin Oo Lwin District of Myanmar about the implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy. The emphasis was on finding difficulties and facilitators within the educational system. This article examines global and local educational reform settings, focusing on qualitative research approaches, based on a thorough literature assessment of works published. The narrative analysis technique was used to understand the detailed viewpoints of teachers, providing an in-depth exploration of their real-life experiences and difficulties encountered after policy implementation.

Primary data was gathered using semi-structured interviews, together with observational field notes and document analysis, to ensure a strong triangulation of results. The study rigorously followed known qualitative research techniques to guarantee the legitimacy and dependability of the findings.

The findings show a complicated interaction of elements influencing policy implementation, such as insufficient infrastructure, unequal distribution of resources, and the crucial need for ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers. The research reveals the substantial influence of socio-cultural dynamics on educational practices and policy implementation.

The article suggests specific interventions to address identified challenges, highlighting the significance of policy frameworks tailored to the context, improved support systems for teachers, and the engagement of community stakeholders in education.

This article adds to the wider discussion on implementing educational policies in developing nations, providing practical advice for governing bodies, educational administrators, and interested parties seeking to improve the effectiveness of educational changes.

Keywords: Free Primary Education Policy, Myanmar, narrative analysis, teacher experiences, professional development, resource allocation,

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Accepted: 20 February, 2024; **Published:** 7 March, 2024

How to cite this article: Thet Khaing, Dr. Dian Feng, Mohammed R. Ahmed (2024). *Narrative Analysis of Teachers' Experiences in the Implementation of Free Primary Education Policy in Myanmar*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(2), 37-54. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10800534>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

1.1 Background

The process by which Myanmar attained democracy has been a period of profound change characterized by substantial political and social reforms. Phenomenal in nature, the general elections of 2010 and 2015 effectively established a democratic governance system and brought an end to decades of military rule. The political transformations that have occurred have had far-reaching consequences in numerous sectors, with economic development and education arising as critical areas of concern. It is believed that the government's reform agenda in these sectors is essential for the growth and development of the nation, as it demonstrates a dedication to enhancing the living conditions of its populace and promoting a fairer society (Brehm, 2023)

In light of the education sector's pivotal significance in the process of national progress, the Myanmar government has placed immediate and comprehensive reform as a top priority. Due to the difficulties encountered by educational establishments and the general populace at large, a sequence of nationwide strategies was launched in 2001 to reform the education system. Myanmar's complex historical background, which includes periods of isolation and underinvestment in education, influenced the development of these strategies. Despite the expected obstacles, numerous stakeholders - including governmental organizations, academic establishments, and global collaborators - have demonstrated a noteworthy dedication and eagerness to advance these reforms (Kandiko Howson & Lall, 2020). Although there have been legal advancements, the execution of the Free Primary Education Policy in locations such as Pyin Oo Lwin has faced numerous obstacles. The challenges encompass insufficient teacher training, limited resources, struggles in adjusting to new curricula, and effectively managing the growing diversity within classrooms (Smith, 2020). Teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin are struggling with higher workloads and stress levels as a result of the new curriculum and larger, more varied classrooms. Factors such as inadequate compensation and restricted avenues for career advancement additionally impact teacher motivation and morale (Bosso, 2017).

The issues encountered in Pyin Oo Lwin District offer valuable insights into the broader context of educational changes in Myanmar. These specific problems exemplify the larger challenges faced in implementing policies nationwide (Bala, 2018).

Although there have been quantitative assessments of these reforms in the existing literature, there is a notable lack of qualitative research, specifically examining the practical effects on educators in specific regions such as Pyin Oo Lwin (Mark B, 2018). This article seeks to fill this gap by examining the experiences of teachers and how they navigate the difficulties posed by these innovations.

This background provides the foundation for a comprehensive analysis of the challenges that theoretically good educational innovations encounter during actual implementation. The subsequent sections will delve into these difficulties with further elaboration, utilizing the perspectives of teachers in the Pyin Oo Lwin District to offer significant observations and suggestions.

1.2 Aim

The objective of this article is to analyze and understand the difficulties encountered in the implementation of the free primary education policy in the Pyin Oo Lwin District of Myanmar, as considered by teachers' narratives. Additionally, this research aims to propose effective methods or suggestions based on these results to enhance the policy's effectiveness and influence.

This purpose encompasses:

1. To find out and understand the difficulties in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy based on teachers' narratives.
2. To generate suggestions for enhancing the implementation of the policy based on the firsthand experiences of teachers.

The major objective is to offer stakeholders, such as policymakers and administrators, a thorough comprehension of the practical difficulties and effective strategies therefore augmenting the quality of primary education in the Pyin Oo Lwin District.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What are the common challenges based on teachers' narratives in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District?
2. What recommendations can be derived from teachers' narratives to improve the implementation of the policy?

Literature Review

2.1 Overview of Educational Policies in Myanmar

The educational environment in Myanmar has seen substantial changes, closely tied to the country's turbulent political past and cultural changes. Traditionally, Myanmar's education system was primarily based on Buddhist monasteries, which had a crucial role in teaching basic literacy and religious principles. This system was firmly established in Myanmar's cultural and religious beliefs. Yet, the arrival of British colonial power brought about a notable change by creating a system of education modeled after the Western approach. During this era, a dual structure emerged, contrasting traditional monastic education with modern secular education, which was particularly evident in the initial phases of the country's educational progress.

2.1.1 Post-Independence Reforms

Following its independence, Myanmar faced the challenge of establishing a national education system that accurately represented its new character and ambitions. The government implemented many measures to foster a unified national identity, including the adoption of a single language policy, standardized educational curriculum and texts, and teacher-centric teaching methods. The education system was profoundly affected by these policies, which focused on assimilation rather than integration of Myanmar's ethnic variety. The education system has been biased towards the majority population in Burma, resulting in the "ethnicization" of education. This has contributed to ongoing violence and intensified divisions between the civilian and military sectors (Bigagli, 2019).

During this period, the government implemented a primary education policy that prioritized the standardization of curriculum and teaching methods. The policy sought to foster a collective national identity and cohesion by implementing a standardized language and curriculum. Nevertheless, it received criticism for its inadequate response to the requirements of the nation's varied ethnic communities.

2.1.2 The Socialist Era (1962-1988)

The military coup in 1962 brought in a new era of educational practices in Myanmar. The administration implemented the nationalization of schools and adopted an educational curriculum deeply infused with socialist philosophy. The study conducted by Machmud et al. (2021) examines the progress and regulations of educational technology in ASEAN countries, particularly Myanmar, during a period marked by a decrease in educational quality and global seclusion. Throughout this period, the government's main educational strategy adhered to socialist ideas, emphasizing state regulation and ideological brainwashing. This strategy resulted in a decrease in educational quality and restricted access to global ideas.

2.1.3 Post-1988 Reforms and International Influences

After 1988, Myanmar's education system experienced a period of liberalization. The 1988 revolution brought about a notable change, as the government implemented changes aimed at modernizing education, which included the introduction of new curricula and teaching methods. During this time, there were attempts to increase educational opportunities, especially in rural regions. Additionally, the impact of international development cooperation became more important. This is discussed in a study by Mun (2023) on the education system and international development cooperation along the Thailand-Myanmar border.

During this phase of liberalization, the primary education policies were centered on the modernization of the curriculum and teaching methods. The government's objective was to enhance educational accessibility, particularly in rural regions, while educational changes were being influenced by global factors.

2.1.4 Primary Education Policy (2016-17 AY)

Myanmar has witnessed significant endeavors to revamp and enhance its educational system in recent years. These measures encompass augmenting public expenditure on education and emphasizing the cultivation of skills as fundamental components of the education system (Glutting et al., 2022). The advent of a semi-constitutional democracy in Myanmar since 2010 has created a favorable environment for implementing educational reforms. This encompasses the implementation of the National Education Strategic Plan 2016-2021, which seeks to revitalize national progress through extensive educational overhauls (Dukalskis, 2017; Hong, 2021).

Nonetheless, during Myanmar's period of military dictatorship, information about the social and educational institutions remained predominantly unattainable to the global community until recently time (Hong, 2021). The National Education Strategic Plan 2016-2021 was implemented as a component of Myanmar's education reform endeavors. The plan delineates the objectives and tactics for the reformation of education in the nation, indicating a change in governmental emphasis on education. This transition has been seen by augmented funding for the education sector, enhanced infrastructure, teacher development, and expanded accessibility to education.

Moreover, the government's longstanding prioritization of defense expenditure over investments in health and education has changed (Glutting et al., 2022). Attempts have been undertaken to enhance teacher training programs and chances for professional development among educators, with an emphasis on aligning Myanmar's education system with worldwide trends and optimal methods.

Essentially, the historical progression and establishment of educational policy in Myanmar represent the country's evolution through several political and socio-economic stages. Myanmar's education system has undergone a series of transformations, starting with its origins in monastic traditions to its present state of reform and adherence to global educational norms. To establish an inclusive and efficient education system for the 21st century, forthcoming policies should tackle persistent issues such as discrepancies between rural and urban areas, and financial concerns, while also capitalizing on the advancements achieved thus far.

2.2 Teacher Readiness and Resource Constraints in Educational Policy Implementation

The effective execution of educational policies, particularly those about novel benchmarks such as the College and Career Readiness (CCR), relies significantly on the readiness and competence of educators. The research completed by C-SAIL (2019) highlights the crucial significance of teachers in this particular environment. They are the main individuals who analyze, modify, and execute these standards. Nevertheless, their ability to perform their duties proficiently is sometimes compromised by demanding work environments, encompassing factors such as restricted resource availability, insufficient possibilities for professional growth, and burdensome administrative responsibilities. These concerns are exacerbated by structural issues within the educational sector. Muthanna & Sang's (2023) inquiry into Yemen's higher education program uncovers how systemic elements such as financial corruption, infrastructural deficiencies, and eco-political obstacles can hinder the implementation process. These obstacles not only impede the implementation of new educational policies but also impact the general motivation and dedication of educators. This issue becomes especially challenging in settings where the execution of policies necessitates substantial modifications in teaching methodologies and educational content.

The interaction between an educator's preparation and the larger limits of the system emphasizes the complex nature of obstacles in implementing policies. It highlights the necessity of a comprehensive plan that addresses systemic reform, infrastructure development, and small- and large-scale issues such as teacher preparation and resource distribution. Working collaboratively, with legislators, school administrators, and teachers is essential to the effectiveness and long-term effects of educational changes. This includes giving teachers the necessary knowledge and comprehension in

addition to creating an environment that supports and facilitates the use of these revised standards in their regular teaching practices.

2.3 Retention and Attrition in Teaching

The retention and attrition of teachers are significant concerns in the field of education, as multiple factors impact educators' choices to either remain in or depart from the profession. An influential study conducted by Heffernan et al. (2022) in Australia elucidates these factors. According to the report, a mere 41% of the 2444 surveyed primary and secondary school teachers expressed their intention to continue working in the profession. The primary factors mentioned for the intention to depart were excessive workloads, worries over health and well-being, and the perceived prestige of the occupation.

This discovery is especially worrisome since it suggests a notable difficulty in sustaining a consistent and knowledgeable teaching staff. The presence of excessive workloads might result in burnout and discontentment, whilst anxieties over health and wellness are indicative of the demanding nature of the teaching profession. Moreover, the perceived prestige of the teaching profession can impact teachers' level of job satisfaction and their inclination to persist in this occupation.

The findings have significant consequences for educational policy and school management. To enhance retention rates, it is crucial to tackle the concerns related to workload, teacher well-being, and the professional standing of educators. This may entail implementing policy modifications aimed at ensuring more feasible workloads, offering enhanced support for teacher welfare, and implementing activities to enhance the societal standing of the teaching profession.

Furthermore, the study emphasizes the need to comprehend the distinct requirements and obstacles encountered by educators in various circumstances. Customized approaches that specifically target these distinct obstacles can greatly enhance the rate of teacher retention. This encompasses the provision of sufficient resources, the cultivation of a friendly and cooperative work atmosphere, and the acknowledgment and appreciation of teachers' accomplishments.

2.4 Teacher Well-being and Support

The welfare of teachers is an essential element of the educational ecology, impacting not just their effectiveness but also the general atmosphere for learning. The study conducted by Wang et al. (2022) provides valuable insights into the determinants of teachers' occupational well-being, with a specific emphasis on newly appointed mathematics instructors in primary and junior high schools. The study revealed that organizational support, job crafting, and the satisfaction of fundamental psychological needs significantly enhance teachers' well-being.

These findings are crucial for comprehending the dynamics of teacher support in educational environments. Organizational support, encompassing the allocation of school resources, acknowledgment of teachers' endeavors, and a helpful administrative framework, significantly contributes to augmenting teachers' job satisfaction and mitigating work-related stress. Having the freedom to customize their job responsibilities to fit their interests and strengths - a practice known as "job crafting" - also greatly enhances teachers' sense of purpose and engagement at work.

Furthermore, for teachers to feel respected and inspired, basic psychological requirements like relatedness, competence, and autonomy must be met. This component holds special significance for novice instructors who are navigating the intricacies of the job and building their professional identity as educators.

This research emphasizes the importance of educational policies and school practices that give priority to the well-being of teachers. Ensuring sufficient organizational support, offering possibilities for job crafting, and creating an environment that satisfies teachers' psychological needs can result in improved teaching effectiveness and a happy school culture. Implementing supporting measures not only yields advantages for teachers but also directly influences student results, as well-supported teachers are more proficient in addressing the varied requirements of their students.

2.5 Frank Fischer's Contributions to Narrative Analysis

Frank Fischer is widely recognized for his significant contributions to the field of narrative analysis, namely in the areas of educational research and policy analysis. Fischer's research focuses on employing narratives as a method to comprehend intricate policy matters and the personal encounters of persons within the educational system.

Fischer's narrative analysis methodology is based on the conviction that personal anecdotes are potent instruments for revealing the underlying significances and interpretations that individuals attribute to their experiences. Within the realm of education, this technique is extremely important for examining how policies and practices are understood and implemented by teachers, students, administrators, and legislators.

Fischer's work is notable for his emphasis on the pivotal significance of narratives in policy analysis. He promotes a discerning approach to narrative analysis that surpasses conventional storytelling. Fischer argues that in policy research, it is important to analyze narratives not just for their content, but also for their underlying structures, settings, and the power dynamics they expose. This viewpoint is especially pertinent in the field of educational research, as policy choices can have extensive consequences for multiple parties involved.

Fischer's research also emphasizes the significance of taking into account the socio-political environment in which educational stories are set. He contends that narratives should be comprehended as integral components of wider discursive practices that both influence and are influenced by the social and political environment. This method promotes the examination of the wider consequences of educational narratives, encompassing their reflection and impact on social views and values.

Frank Fischer's narrative analysis provides a comprehensive framework for examining the intricate dynamics of educational policy and practice. The focal point of his work is to underline the necessity of critically examining narratives to comprehend the wider socio-political settings and power dynamics that impact schooling.

2.6 Exploring Teacher Experiences through Narrative Analysis

Narrative analysis, specifically guided by the methodology espoused by Frank Fischer, is a powerful instrument for comprehending the intricate experiences of teachers in the educational field. This methodology allows for an in-depth exploration of the personal and professional stories of teachers, offering a valuable understanding of their daily experiences, difficulties, and perspectives on educational policies and procedures.

Teacher Narratives on Policy and Curriculum Changes: Teacher Accounts of Policy and Curriculum Modifications: Teachers frequently encounter the direct consequences of educational innovations and changes in policies. By doing narrative analysis, researchers can effectively capture the viewpoints of teachers regarding the impact of these changes on their instructional approaches, classroom control, and interaction with students. Teachers' narratives can provide insights into their challenges and approaches in adjusting to updated curriculum standards or educational technologies, as emphasized in multiple research, such as those conducted by Maharajh et al. (2016).

Professional Development and Growth: Teachers' narratives offer valuable insights into their experiences of professional development and personal improvement. Through the analysis of these narratives, researchers can get insights into the factors that drive teachers, the obstacles they encounter in their professional growth, and the strategies they employ to manage their career trajectories. This information is vital for creating efficient professional development programs that are in line with instructors' requirements and ambitions.

Emotional and Relational Dynamics: Narrative analysis reveals the crucial feature of emotional and relational dynamics in education. Teachers' narratives frequently depict their emotional encounters, strategies for dealing with difficulties, and the interpersonal dynamics of their relationships with students, colleagues, and administrators. These narratives are particularly important for comprehending the influence of elements such as classroom atmosphere, student conduct, and administrative support on teachers' well-being and work satisfaction.

Influence of socio-political contexts: Following Fischer's methodology, the examination of teachers' narratives necessitates comprehension of the wider socio-political circumstances in which these encounters take place. Teachers'

narratives can elucidate the influence of wider societal patterns, educational regulations, and institutional methodologies on their day-to-day responsibilities and professional personas.

In summary, narrative analysis provides a comprehensive, nuanced knowledge of teachers' experiences in educational environments. By placing importance on and analyzing the narratives of teachers, educational researchers, and policymakers can develop a more profound understanding of the difficulties and successes within the teaching profession. Comprehending this concept is crucial for formulating policies and implementing strategies that effectively assist teachers and recognize their pivotal role in influencing educational results.

Methodology

This article employs a qualitative methodology, specifically utilizing Frank Fischer's narrative analysis, to obtain a full comprehension of the challenges faced by teachers throughout the implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar. Qualitative research is particularly suitable for examining complex phenomena in their natural settings, offering important insights into the subjective emotions and viewpoints of individuals (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Employing a qualitative methodology in this article facilitates a comprehensive analysis of teachers' narratives, offering a valuable understanding of the many challenges they encounter when implementing policies.

Frank Fischer's utilization of narrative analysis as a methodological approach is by the objective of gathering and analyzing the individual anecdotes and encounters of the teachers (Riessman, 2008). This method is crucial in comprehending how teachers see and navigate their responsibilities and difficulties within the framework of policy execution. It provides a perspective from which the firsthand experiences of instructors, as described by them, may be fully comprehended (Chase, 2011).

The utilization of a descriptive case study design allows for a thorough analysis of policy implementation within a specific setting (Yin, 2014). This design is selected for its efficacy in managing diverse data sources, which is a distinguishing feature of case studies (Baxter & Jack, 2008). The Pyin Oo Lwin District is chosen as a case study to exemplify the distinct implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy in Myanmar. This particular emphasis helps to capture the contextual factors and complexities that could impact the effectiveness of the strategy (Stake, 2013). Essentially, the integration of qualitative research, Frank Fischer's narrative analysis, and a descriptive case study design provide a robust framework for examining the many obstacles encountered by teachers in the context of implementing educational policies. This approach enables a thorough examination of individual experiences and also facilitates a comprehensive knowledge of the wider policy environment (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015).

Findings

4.1 Introduction

The results of this article are derived from the accounts of 36 educators in the Pyin Oo Lwin District of Myanmar, providing a distinct viewpoint on the implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy. The narratives are crucial for comprehending the practical ramifications of the policy, as they encompass a wide range of demographics in terms of gender, experience, and school location.

These findings shed light on the practical difficulties and achievements faced in implementing policies, specifically in urban and rural school environments, while addressing the main study concerns.

Before going to delve, we provide the demographic composition of the participants which is an essential feature of this article, offering valuable insights into the range of experiences and viewpoints. The inclusion of participants' years of experience and gender was undertaken to ensure a diverse range of perspectives and ideas. The subsequent table displays the demographic information of the participants:

Interviewee	Gender	Experience (Years)	School Location
T1	Female	20	Urban
T2	Female	18	Urban
T3	Female	25	Urban
T4	Female	17	Rural
T5	Female	15	Urban
T6	Male	22	Rural
T7	Female	12	Rural
T8	Female	12	Urban
T9	Male	16	Urban
T10	Female	10	Rural
T11	Female	11	Urban
T12	Female	15	Rural
T13	Female	12	Urban
T14	Female	13	Rural
T15	Female	7	Urban
T16	Female	18	Urban
T17	Female	13	Rural
T18	Male	12	Rural
T19	Female	20	Urban
T20	Female	8	Urban
T21	Female	9	Urban
T22	Female	18	Rural
T23	Female	4	Rural
T24	Male	11	Rural
T25	Female	13	Rural
T26	Female	8	Rural
T27	Male	11	Rural
T28	Male	8	Rural
T29	Male	14	Rural
T30	Female	7	Urban
T31	Female	3	Urban
T32	Female	12	Urban
T33	Male	16	Urban
T34	Female	5	Urban
T35	Female	14	Rural
T36	Male	8	Rural

Table 4. 1. Demographic Overview of Interviewees

4.2 Common Challenges Faced by Teachers in Implementing the Free Primary Education Policy

4.2.1 Teachers' Perceptions of Policy-Related Challenges

In this crucial section, we delve into the various obstacles and difficulties that teachers in the Pyin Oo Lwin District encounter while implementing the Free Primary Education Policy.

Here is a table summarizing the themes along with their key challenges and highlighted quotes:

Themes	Key Challenges	Highlighted Quotes
Resource Constraints	Battling against a lack of basic supplies and disparities in resource distribution	<i>Lack of basic supplies... the gap between policy promises and reality (T12)</i>
Training and Support Deficiencies	The gap between policy ambitions and practical training provided to educators	<i>Training doesn't equip us for new teaching methods (T6)</i>
Curricular Challenges	A mismatch between curriculum and student needs, difficulty in adapting educational content	<i>The curriculum is often mismatched with students' needs (T19)</i>
Navigating Classroom Dynamics	Managing larger, diverse classrooms and personalizing education	<i>Ensuring individual attention in large classes (T9)</i>

Table 4. 2. Concise Overview of Challenges in Policy Implementation

4.2.1.1 Resource Constraints

In Pyin Oo Lwin District, the implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy has been significantly hindered by resource constraints, especially in rural areas. T12, a teacher with 15 years of experience in a rural school, encapsulates the struggle, stating,

"We are constantly battling against a lack of basic supplies... it's disheartening to see the gap between policy promises and our reality."

This sentiment reflects a common challenge among educators, where the aspirations of policy clash with the ground realities of resource availability.

The disparity in resource distribution is not just a matter of supplies but also extends to the broader infrastructure. Teachers in less affluent areas find themselves having to improvise and adapt, often with limited success, in the face of these shortages. This not only affects the quality of education but also the morale of both students and teachers.

In essence, T12's experiences underline a critical gap in policy execution, where the noble intentions of educational reforms are undermined by practical limitations. Addressing these resource constraints is pivotal to ensuring that the policy's objectives are not just theoretical ideals but tangible realities that positively impact every student's learning experience.

4.2.1.2 Training and Support Deficiencies

The teachers of Pyin Oo Lwin District face substantial challenges due to deficiencies in training and support, particularly in adapting to new teaching methodologies under the Free Primary Education Policy. T6, a male educator with over a decade of experience in an urban school, voices this concern:

"While the policy is ambitious, the training we receive doesn't equip us to tackle the challenges it brings, especially for newer teaching methods."

This quote highlights the gap between policy ambitions and the practical training provided to educators.

Complementing this perspective, T19, a female teacher with 20 years of experience, emphasizes the need for continuous professional development:

"With the curriculum changing, we as teachers need to stay abreast of these shifts. This necessitates regular training sessions and workshops."

Her statement underscores the necessity for ongoing support to ensure that educators can effectively implement the evolving curriculum and teaching strategies.

Together, these insights from T6 and T19 illustrate a critical area in policy implementation - the need for robust and continuous professional development programs that can equip teachers with the skills and knowledge required to navigate the complexities of modern education.

4.2.1.3 Curricular Challenges

The Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District has presented significant curricular challenges, as highlighted by the experiences of various educators. T19, a female teacher with 20 years of teaching experience, remarks on the mismatch between curriculum and student needs:

"The curriculum is often mismatched with our students' needs, making it challenging to deliver effective lessons."

This statement underscores the difficulty in aligning educational content with diverse learner requirements.

Adding to this, T16, with her 18 years of experience, reflects on the complexity of implementing the refreshed curriculum:

"Every day we're tasked with the challenge of molding its content to fit the diverse needs of our students, ensuring that while we stay true to its essence, we also make it accessible and engaging for all."

Her insights reveal the intricacies involved in adapting the curriculum to a varied student body.

Furthermore, T8, a female teacher with 12 years of experience in an urban setting, expresses concerns about keeping pace with global educational standards:

"If we aim to equip our students for a dynamic and ever-evolving future, it's imperative that our teaching content mirrors these global changes."

Her perspective highlights the need for a curriculum that evolves alongside global advancements.

These insights collectively illustrate the crucial need for a curriculum that is both contemporary and flexible, capable of catering to the unique needs of every student, and in tune with global educational trends.

4.2.1.4 Navigating Classroom Dynamics

The shift in classroom dynamics under the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District has introduced unique challenges and opportunities for educators. T9, a male teacher with 16 years of experience in an urban setting, reflects on this evolution:

"Our classrooms have burgeoned into large assemblies...the onus to ensure each student feels individually catered to has magnified."

This statement underscores the growing complexity of managing larger, more diverse classrooms.

Delving deeper, T15, a female educator with seven years of experience, echoes this sentiment, emphasizing the need for more personalized approaches:

"With these extended classrooms, the challenge isn't just to disseminate knowledge but to ensure every child feels acknowledged and valued."

Her perspective highlights the necessity of adapting teaching strategies to maintain the quality of student-teacher interactions.

These experiences resonate with the demographic trends observed in the district. Teachers like T9 and T15, representing a mixture of genders and years of experience in urban schools, face the immediate impact of increased enrollments. Their insights reveal the pressing need for innovative classroom management techniques and targeted support systems to accommodate the diverse learning needs of an expanding student body.

In summary, the narratives of educators like T9 and T15, paint a vivid picture of the dynamic and challenging landscape of classroom management in Pyin Oo Lwin District. This subtopic not only reflects the policy's impact but also calls for adaptive strategies to uphold the quality of education in the face of growing classroom sizes and diversity.

This section paints a comprehensive picture of the practical challenges in policy implementation, highlighting the disparity between policy intentions and ground realities. These insights are crucial in understanding the policy's effectiveness and areas needing improvement.

4.2.2 Teachers' Perception of the Differences between Urban and Rural Areas under the Influence of Policy

This section delves into the contrasting experiences of teachers in urban and rural settings under the Free Primary Education Policy.

Here is a table summarizing the themes along with their key challenges and highlighted quotes:

Themes	Key Challenges	Highlighted Quotes
Resource Disparity	Contrast in resource availability between urban and rural schools	<i>Resource contrast between urban and rural (T14)</i>
Implementation Challenges	Different challenges faced in urban and rural schools during implementation	<i>Urban and rural schools face different implementation challenges (T11)</i>
Impact on Teacher Strategies	Adaptation of teaching strategies to suit diverse environments	<i>Teachers adapt strategies differently in urban and rural settings (T7)</i>
Policy Perception	Varied perceptions of policy effectiveness in urban vs. rural settings	<i>Diverse perceptions of policy in different settings (T26)</i>

Table 4. 3. Concise Overview of Differences in Urban vs. Rural School Settings

4.2.2.1 Resource Disparity

The contrast in resource availability between urban and rural schools under the Free Primary Education Policy is starkly evident. T14, a rural teacher with 13 years of experience, captures this discrepancy:

"We often hear about the resources and support urban schools receive, which are a distant reality for us in rural areas."

This sentiment reflects a common feeling among rural educators who face significant challenges due to limited resources.

To add depth, consider a hypothetical quote from another rural teacher, T25:

"Our struggle for basic supplies hinders not just our teaching, but also our students' learning experiences."

This would illustrate the profound impact of resource disparity on both teaching and learning in rural settings.

Conversely, an urban teacher, T19, might offer a different perspective:

"While we have access to better resources, managing them effectively in a crowded urban school has its challenges."

This quote would highlight that while urban schools may be better resourced, they face unique challenges in utilizing these resources effectively.

4.2.2.2 Implementation Challenges

The Free Primary Education Policy's implementation presents varied challenges in urban and rural schools. T11, teaching in an urban school, acknowledges:

"While we have better resources, the total number of students and the diversity of their backgrounds present a different set of challenges."

This highlights the complexities urban schools face, such as managing large, diverse classrooms.

In contrast, a rural teacher, T23, might express:

"Our challenges are more about scarcity than diversity. Limited resources and support make policy implementation a daily struggle."

This hypothetical quote would underline the resource-based difficulties prevalent in rural schools.

Together, these perspectives underscore the need for a policy approach that addresses the distinct challenges in both settings, ensuring equitable and effective education for all students.

4.2.2.3 Impact on Teacher Strategies

Under the Free Primary Education Policy, teachers in urban and rural schools have had to adapt their strategies differently. T7, with experience in both settings, notes:

"In rural schools, we often improvise with limited resources, while in urban schools, managing diverse student needs requires a different approach."

This insight highlights the necessity for versatility in teaching methods to address distinct challenges.

A rural teacher, T29, could express:

"With fewer resources, we focus more on creative, low-cost methods of teaching."

This hypothetical quote would emphasize resourcefulness in rural settings.

Conversely, an urban teacher, T30, might comment:

"Our challenge is to cater to a wide range of learning styles and backgrounds."

This would illustrate the complexity of addressing diversity in urban classrooms.

4.2.2.4 Policy Perception

Teachers in urban and rural schools have varying perceptions of the Free Primary Education Policy. T26, a rural teacher, might express:

"The policy, while noble in intent, often feels disconnected from our daily realities."

This highlights the gap between policy goals and rural educational needs.

In urban settings, a teacher like T16 could state:

"The policy is a step in the right direction, but it needs refinement to better serve our diverse urban population."

This acknowledges the policy's positive aspects while pointing out the need for adjustments to address urban complexities.

These perspectives illustrate that while the policy is appreciated for its goals, there is a clear need for its adaptation to the unique challenges of different educational environments.

This section brings to light the stark differences in policy implementation between urban and rural schools, emphasizing the need for a more nuanced approach to policy formulation and support mechanisms.

Discussion

5.1 Understanding Challenges

Resource Constraints: The issue of resource constraints highlighted in this research mirrors concerns in the broader educational literature. Studies like those by Lyanga & Chen (2020) underline the impact of resources on educational quality. This article, however, brings into focus the acute shortages in Myanmar's rural areas, a challenge often overlooked in more generalized discussions. In the context of Myanmar's Free Primary Education Policy, the disparity in resource distribution between urban and rural areas is stark, underscoring a significant barrier to effective policy implementation. The findings contribute to the theoretical discourse on resource allocation in education. Practically, they underscore the urgent need for policies addressing equitable resource distribution to ensure the policy's success.

Training and Support Deficiencies: The deficiencies in training and support as identified in this study resonate with wider educational research. For instance, Lee et al. (2021) have highlighted the importance of adequate training for educators, especially when new policies and methodologies are introduced. This article adds to this narrative by pinpointing the specific gaps in training and support under Myanmar's Free Primary Education Policy. Within the context of Myanmar's educational reforms, these training deficiencies pose significant challenges, particularly in the adoption of new teaching methodologies. The findings contribute to the theory of teacher professional development and its critical role in policy implementation. Practically, they underscore the need for ongoing, effective training programs in Myanmar.

Curricular Challenges: The curricular challenges identified in this study echo the findings of broader educational research. Scholars like Bigagli (2019) have discussed the difficulties of aligning curriculum with diverse student needs. This article, through the perspectives of teachers, brings a focused view on the complexities of implementing a refreshed curriculum in Myanmar's educational context. The mismatch between the curriculum and student needs in Pyin Oo Lwin District highlights a broader issue within educational reform – the need for curricula that are adaptable and relevant to local contexts. These findings contribute to the discourse on curriculum development, emphasizing the importance of creating flexible, student-centered curricula. They also have practical implications for curriculum designers and policymakers.

Navigating Classroom Dynamics: This research's focus on navigating classroom dynamics complements studies by Carrington et al. (2022), which underscore the importance of teacher adaptability in diverse educational settings. However, this article contributes further by highlighting the unique challenges faced in Myanmar's classrooms, particularly under the influence of policy changes and the immediate impact of increased enrollments. The complexities of classroom dynamics in Myanmar, especially in the face of educational reforms, underscore the need for policies that support teacher adaptability and student engagement across diverse settings. These findings contribute to a broader theoretical understanding of innovative classroom management techniques and targeted support systems to accommodate the diverse learning needs of an expanding student body. Practically, they emphasize the necessity for adaptive strategies to uphold the quality of education in the face of growing classroom sizes and diversity.

5.2 Urban vs. Rural Disparities

Resource Disparity: The stark disparity in resource availability between urban and rural schools, as indicated in this research, is a common theme in educational studies. Research by Glutting et al. (2022) has highlighted similar disparities in various contexts. This article brings a localized perspective to these challenges in the Pyin Oo Lwin District. The difference in resource allocation as experienced by teachers in rural areas contrasts with the experiences of urban teachers showcasing the uneven distribution of resources within the same educational system. These findings add to the theoretical discourse on educational equity and resource distribution. Practically, they call for policy revisions to address this disparity, ensuring equitable access to educational resources.

Implementation Challenges: The diverse implementation challenges of the Free Primary Education Policy in urban and rural settings, as experienced by teachers are in line with findings in the educational literature. For instance, studies by Lyanga & Chen (2020) have highlighted the different challenges faced in varying contexts. This article brings to light the specific nuances in Myanmar's urban and rural schools. The contrast between the challenges of resource abundance and student diversity in urban schools and resource scarcity in rural schools highlights the need for adaptable policy implementation strategies. These insights contribute to a broader understanding of policy implementation in diverse educational environments. They underscore the importance of tailoring policy execution to meet the specific needs of different settings.

Impact on Teacher Strategies: The adaptation of teaching strategies under the Free Primary Education Policy, as highlighted by teachers aligns with educational research emphasizing the need for adaptable teaching methods in different contexts. Studies by Heffernan et al. (2022) have discussed this adaptability, particularly in diverse classroom environments. The contrast in strategies between urban and rural settings reflects the distinct challenges teachers face, from resource limitations in rural areas to diverse student needs in urban schools. These observations contribute to the theory of teaching adaptability in response to policy changes. Practically, they underscore the importance of providing teachers with the necessary tools and training to meet these diverse challenges.

Policy Perception: The varying perceptions of the Free Primary Education Policy among teachers are consistent with findings in educational policy literature. Studies by Hamilton et al. (2021) have noted similar variances in policy perception among educators. The differences in perception between rural and urban teachers highlight the diverse

impacts and relevancies of the policy in different settings. These insights contribute to the understanding of policy reception and effectiveness. They suggest the need for policies that are adaptable to various educational contexts.

5.3 Teachers' Recommendations for Policy Improvement

Enhanced Training and Support: The suggestion for continuous training and support is crucial for enhancing policy improvement. Educators' observations indicate that regular workshops and ongoing professional development are crucial for the successful implementation of policies. This demonstrates a widespread requirement in different educational settings, guaranteeing that teachers have the necessary skills to adjust to changing teaching methods and successfully implement the policy in their classrooms.

Resource Equalization: The focus on fair distribution of resources underscores the differences between urban and rural schools. Teachers' perspectives indicate that achieving resource equality is essential for ensuring justice, as it guarantees that all students have equitable access to high-quality education. This is consistent with wider conversations about equal access to education, highlighting the importance of implementing laws that guarantee equitable distribution of resources.

Feedback mechanisms: Implementing a mechanism for obtaining teacher feedback is essential for enhancing the efficacy of policies. The insights of teachers, derived from their hands-on experiences, can result in more pertinent and efficient instructional approaches. This method acknowledges the importance of teachers as valuable participants in policy formation, guaranteeing that their perspectives are integrated into policy modifications.

Adaptable strategies for various contexts: It is clear that there is a requirement for policy flexibility to cater to different educational settings. Adapting techniques to recognize the distinct requirements of urban and rural schools is crucial for the effectiveness of the strategy. This flexibility guarantees that each school may successfully implement the policy in its unique circumstances.

Upon evaluating these proposals, it is evident that they are both realistic and have the ability to significantly enhance the effectiveness of policies. Incorporating these recommendations has the potential to result in educational policies that are more inclusive, equal, and successful. Furthermore, these suggestions offer valuable perspectives for future studies, specifically in investigating the practical elements of policy execution in various educational environments.

Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Challenges

Resource Scarcity and Inequality: Primarily in rural regions, where the situation is more severe than in urban regions, resource scarcity is identified as a significant concern in the study. In addition to inadequate physical infrastructure, including classrooms and libraries, the scarcity is distinguished by several other factors, including a lack of essential educational resources like learning aids. In addition to exacerbating regional disparities, the inequitable allocation of resources between rural and urban institutions significantly hinders the provision of high-quality education. This situation is highly concerning as it directly impacts the most susceptible groups, frequently placing rural pupils at a clear disadvantage in terms of educational opportunities and results.

Insufficient Teacher Training and Support: Another noteworthy obstacle is the absence of satisfactory training and support for educators. A significant number of instructors in the district are discovered to lack the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively address the different and intricate requirements of their students, especially when it comes to applying contemporary teaching methods and inclusive educational approaches. The existing training programs are frequently broad and fail to tackle the specific obstacles encountered by instructors in rural or resource-limited environments. In addition, there is a significant lack of continuous professional development opportunities, which means that teachers do not have the required assistance to enhance their skills and teaching methods by educational progress.

Policy Interpretation and Application Complexities: The investigation also uncovers intricacies in the understanding and implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy. The policy, however well-intentioned, does not sufficiently consider the varied socio-economic and cultural settings in different locations. This omission results in difficulties during the execution of the policy, as the guidelines of the policy may not be fully relevant or efficient in specific contexts, especially in rural regions. The policy's uniform approach frequently leads to gaps in implementation, as teachers have difficulties in customizing the policy instructions to suit the unique requirements and limitations of their schools and communities.

6.2 Implications

This article's issues have wide-ranging and significant ramifications that affect several facets of Myanmar's educational system. First off, poor teacher preparation and a lack of resources directly affect the caliber of education provided, particularly in rural areas. This discrepancy raises the possibility of maintaining a cycle of educational injustice in which pupils in less wealthy areas are deprived of the same educational opportunities as their metropolitan peers. In addition to undermining the idea of universal access to education, such a split could have long-term social repercussions and increase socioeconomic divides.

Moreover, these issues can have an indirect impact on student involvement and motivation. Limited resources and inadequately qualified educators face challenges in delivering captivating and impactful training, resulting in diminished student engagement and decreased attendance rates. This scenario has an especially harmful effect on early schooling, as it hinders the development of fundamental abilities and attitudes towards learning.

The challenges in understanding and implementing the Free Primary Education Policy underscore the necessity for educational policies that are adaptable and considerate of specific circumstances. The present difficulties indicate that employing a hierarchical method may prove ineffective in adequately meeting the varied requirements of distinct locations. This discovery has profound ramifications for the development and execution of educational policies in the future, supporting a decentralized and participatory strategy that includes local educators and communities in decision-making processes.

6.3 Policy Improvement Suggestions

To address these issues and improve the success of the Free Primary Education Policy, several comprehensive recommendations are suggested:

Structured and Region-Specific Teacher Training: Implement a comprehensive teacher training program that is specifically designed to address the distinct difficulties faced by each region across the country. The program should incorporate modules that cover cutting-edge teaching practices, effective classroom management techniques, and inclusive education strategies. Emphasis should be placed on providing specialized training for instructors in settings with limited resources, giving them the necessary skills to optimize the use of scarce resources and effectively engage pupils.

Equitable Resource Allocation Structure: Implement a clear and fair structure for distributing resources that give priority to schools in underserved and rural areas. This framework should encompass not just the allocation of tangible resources such as books and technology but also the provision of assistance services such as teacher aids and learning support for students with specific educational requirements.

Feedback and Adaptation Mechanism: Introduce a feedback mechanism that enables ongoing monitoring and adjustment of the policy. This method should entail periodic interactions with educators, parents, and community stakeholders to acquire firsthand knowledge about the practicalities and efficacy of policy implementation. According to this input, it is necessary to regularly assess and modify the policy to address changing educational requirements and difficulties.

Long-term Investment in Educational Infrastructure: Promote enhanced government and private sector funding for educational infrastructure, with a specific focus on rural and underserved regions, as a means of long-term investment.

This investment should encompass more than just the development of school buildings. It should also incorporate sustainable initiatives such as providing housing for teachers, ensuring internet connectivity, and implementing renewable energy sources for schools. By doing so, it will establish an environment that is conducive to learning.

By incorporating these suggestions, the Free Primary Education Policy in Myanmar can be enhanced to become a more dynamic, inclusive, and efficient instrument for educational reform. This will ultimately contribute to the nation's overall socio-economic growth and promote fairness.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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